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User guide for the FGMT navigation system

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1. INTRODUCTION

The "*FGMT_NavigationSystem*" script represents the part of the code related to the navigation system of the three robots that make up the robotic array of seismic sensors for the *Flexible Grid Mapping Tool* project.

Referring to the technical report [1], this code is to be loaded on the Crumbuino Mega (equivalent to Arduino Mega 2560), installed on the Mobile Unit Board (MUB), of each Robot Unit (RU) and does not include the data acquisition and communication part with the Control Unit (CU), which is in charge of the Data Unit Board (DUB). The navigation system can be broken down into a set of subtasks:

- Communication with the DUB for the reception/transmission of commands/information on the system status.
- Line Follower technique on the Main Pattern (MP).
- Reading of the barcodes.
- Exit from the MP in correspondence with the right barcode and calibration for the right orientation of entry in the relative Area of Interest (Aoi).
- Off-line movement, following the X and Y coordinates of the position communicated by the DUB.
- Obstacle avoidance.
- Extension and blocking of the front leg during the data acquisition phase.
- Search for the line and return to the MP.
- Search for the battery charging area, waiting for the seismic data collected to be processed by the CU.

For all the details, paragraph 4 of the technical report [1] can be consulted, entitled "*Mobile Unit*".

The document is organized as follows: in paragraph 2, the functions introduced in the "*setup()*" macro function will be described, indicating what the input/output parameters are and mentioning what happens, conceptually, inside them. In paragraph 3, instead, the functions used in the "*loop()*" macro function will be described, in the same way as the previous paragraph, also accompanied by a logical description of the code structure.

2.SETUP()

In this part of the code, all the pins used are set, the servomotor for the front leg and the infrared sensors are calibrated. Note that, in order to use the latter, it is necessary to install the relative library [3].

- `initPins()`:
 - input: none.
 - output: none.
 - description: all the necessary pins (INPUT/OUTPUT) are initialized; in particular, the infrared sensors (Figure 1) [2] of the relative bar for Line Following are chosen and the serial communication (UART2) with the DUB is initialized for receiving commands/sending data on the system status.

Figure 1. QTR-HD-25A Reflectance Sensor Array (top).
Bar sensors actually used (down)

- `calibrateServo()`:
 - input: none.
 - output: none.
 - description: initialization of the servo motor position (leg fully raised).

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- *rotateServo(unsigned long duration)*:
 - input: time period during which to rotate the servomotor. (ms)
 - output: none.
 - description: a timer is initialized during which the servo motor rotates at a certain speed. After a time equal to “*duration*”, it is blocked. This function is used, for example, to allow the leg to extend completely, starting from the initialization position (leg completely raised).

 - *calibrationIR()*:
 - input: none.
 - output: none.
 - description: function used to calibrate the infrared sensors used for the Line Follower technique. A RU is placed in the starting position, on the MP, and rotated clockwise and counterclockwise, for a certain number of seconds, during which the values, corresponding to the reflections of the infrared rays, are recorded on the corresponding sensors of the bar, in order to find the maximums and minimums and set the dynamic range of operation of the unit. This operation must be performed for each RU. For more details see the documentation of the infrared sensors library [3].

 - *MotorAISR()*:
 - input: none.
 - output: none.
 - description: this is the ISR for the left motor. It is called every time an interrupt is sent by the encoder mounted on the same motor, through the relative pin connected to the microcontroller. The encoder output is a square wave with a frequency equal to 16 times that of the rotation of the motor shaft (16 counts per revolution), considering the reduction ratio, approximately 1633 that of the coupled wheel (1633 counts per revolution)[4]. Each count can be converted, knowing the dimensions of the wheel, into centimeters traveled by the latter and therefore by the robot, so this output is used to measure the distance traveled and the sustained speed. At each rising edge an interrupt is requested for which the “*MotorAISR()*” function will be executed, in which the variable “*encL*” is simply incremented count after count. This value, indicating the amount of rotation of the motor shaft, will be cyclically converted into distance (cm) traveled by the RU through a conversion factor (“*STEP2CM*”).

 - *MotorBISR()*:
 - input: none.
 - output: none.
 - description: Same goes for the previous function. This time the variable that is incremented is the variable “*encR*”.
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3.LOOP()

In Figure 3 is shown the flowchart, in a simplified form, of the "loop()" function. Basically, there are two nested finite state machines corresponding to two state variables, "**robotState**" and "**movementState**", whose values are updated cyclically based on the commands from the CU, through the DUB. The first one can assume three values, based on the position of each RU on the MP:

- "**LINE_FOLLOWING**" → RU in a generic position along the MP.
- "**DETECTING_BARCODE**" → RU detects the presence of a barcode and starts counting the black bars it is composed of, in order to identify it correctly.
- "**BARCODE_DETECTED**" → once the barcode has been identified, it can be compared with the one indicated by the CU via the DUB.

The second one can assume two values, based on the commands received by the MUB:

- "**STOP**" → blocking of the RU at any point of the MP or of an AoI due to the reception of a "stop" command. For simplicity, no stop signal will be heard during the "**DETECTING_BARCODE**" state.
- "**MOTION**" → RU in motion state, following a "restart" command or a position to be reached for the purpose of a seismic measurement.

Figure 2. Sketch of the setup and the navigation scheme. The sketch illustrates: the main track (black rectangle) with the global reference system (red) and bar-code markers alongside; a few areas of interest (blue rectangles) with their own local reference system (black arrows), the charging stations (C.S); three navigating robots.

Figure 3. loop() function flowchart

By following the flowchart, can be seen in which states the two finite state machines are initialized. The *Start* phase is followed by a check of the serial buffer to verify whether or not a command has been received from the DUB and to check its correctness (commands other than the three indicated will be discarded). Based on what is found, the states are updated otherwise they remain the same as those set at the beginning. For simplicity of representation, the "*MovementState*" finite state machine is not shown in the flowchart, whose states are considered in the case of "*LINE_FOLLOWING*", "*BARCODE_DETECTED*" and outside the MP (reaching position in Aol). Before understanding in which point of the MP the RU is located (therefore in which branch of the flowchart), the position with respect to the infrared sensor bar of the black line on which to perform the Line Following is detected, using a specific function of the infrared sensors library [3]. Based on the reading made, the control variable to be applied to the physical system (voltage to the motors) will then be determined.

In the case of "*LINE_FOLLOWING*" the PID control is performed first, thanks to the previous reading obtained with the infrared sensors, so the DC motors are driven in order to keep the RU aligned with the MP. The presence of barcodes is also checked using the sensors that are more external to the infrared bar and the "*isOnBarcode(...)*" function, which outputs a boolean value based on which "*robotState*" is updated (more details below). In the case of barcode detection, a timer is initialized to count the black bars that compose it and the state is moved to "*DETECTING_BARCODE*".

Closing the loop, the system remains in this state and therefore continues to count the presence of any black bars until the timer ends ("*barcodeDuration*"). At this point it moves to "*BARCODE_DETECTED*" during which the obtained ID, consistent with the number of bars calculated (1, 2 or 3 in this case), is compared with the one requested by the CU. If the two parameters do not coincide, the RU will continue along the MP, returning to "*LINE_FOLLOWING*", looking for the next barcode to identify and compare.

In the case of correspondence and, not yet needing to recharge the battery, the RU will exit the MP and enter the associated Aol in order to reach the point requested by the CU, following its coordinates with respect to the local reference system ("*targetX*, *targetY*") (see Figure 2). Once at the destination, the front leg will be lowered for the data acquisition phase at the end of which the RU will return to the MP, looking for the black line that distinguishes it. Along the outward and return routes, using the digital infrared sensors and dedicated routines, obstacle avoidance maneuvers will be performed, if necessary. As indicated in the graph, during the entire stay in the Aol, UART communication with the DUB will be active and therefore it will be possible to send "*stop*" / "*restart*" commands to the RU with consequent blocking/restarting of the motors in any position.

The system returns to "*LINE_FOLLOWING*" but this time it will not wait for any command (except for the "*stop*" / "*restart*" ones) because it will look for the barcode relating to the battery charging station, since it will be necessary to wait for the CU to process the seismic data just collected. For simplicity, this barcode will be the same as the one previously indicated but, in this phase, the RU will have to go inside the MP where there are no Aols but only charging stations, one for each area (unlike what can be seen in Figure 2). So the system retraces all the previous phases with the only difference being that, once reached the right barcode, it opts for the battery charging branch. In this phase the RU remains in the "*LINE_FOLLOWING*"-"*STOP*" states and at the end of it, once received a new position to reach, it will switch to "*LINE_FOLLOWING*"-"*MOTION*". A return maneuver on the MP will be performed and the work cycle will be repeated.

Now we can move on to a more detailed description of the functions used, as already done in the previous paragraph. The list starts with the simplest and least structured ones, used as "bricks" for the more complex ones, at the bottom.

- *convertDist2Steps(float dist)*:
 - input: distance (cm) to be converted in encoder counts.
 - output: distance expressed in encoder counts (*int*).
 - description: using simple calculations, first the input distance is converted into the corresponding number of wheel revolutions (given the length of its circumference), also considering non-integer results. Then this value is multiplied by the number of encoder counts in one integer wheel revolution (given from the motor datasheet [4]) to obtain the function output.

 - *drive(int powerA, int powerB)*:
 - input: PWM values to drive motors.
 - output: none.
 - description: this is the function that allows to drive the motors. The input signs are used to set the "HIGH"/"LOW" values on the pins related to the motor rotation direction of the relative drivers (H-bridge) [5]. Their modules instead are proportional to the voltages to which the motors are powered and therefore to their rotation speeds.

 - *extendLeg(unsigned long extensionTime)*:
 - input: time during which the robot's leg must remain extended (ms).
 - output: none.
 - description: this is the function, used for the data acquisition phase, that allows to keep the front leg of the RU extended for a period of time given in input. For the extension and retraction of the leg, the previously described function "rotateServo(..)" is used, while to bring the leg back to the upper reference position, having only a continuous rotation servomotor, the function "calibrateServo()" is used.

 - *isNumeric(String str)*:
 - input: character string to check.
 - output: boolean value that indicates whether the input string is all digits or not (*bool*).
 - description: this function verifies that the characters in the received string are all digits. The entire string is checked character by character: if there is at least one character that is not a digit or if there are two commas (decimal values), the value "false" is given in output, otherwise "true".

 - *isOnBarcode(unsigned int *checkAreaSensorVal)*:
 - input: vector in whose components overwrite the readings of the infrared sensors for barcode recognition.
 - output: boolean value that indicates whether the voltage values, read by the pins connected to the infrared sensors, exceed a certain threshold ("barcodeThreshold") or not (*bool*).
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- **description:** function which determines if the robot is on an horizontal black line (first barcode bar) from raw data of sensors reading. In practice, the voltage values are read on the analog input pins to which the infrared sensors are connected (in this case, only one sensor connected to the "A7" pin is used). This value is greater the darker the surface on which the RU is standing and is compared with the *"barcodeThreshold"* variable which corresponds to a threshold value: if it will be greater than the latter, then it will mean that the RU is on the first black bar of a barcode and a *"true"* value will be output, otherwise *"false"*.
 - *hitBreaks(float motorSpeed, char orientation):*
 - **input:** magnitude (*"motorSpeed"*) and direction (*"orientation"*) of the speed at which the RU is traveling.
"orientation" = *"a"* (ahead), *"b"* (behind), *"l"* (left), *"r"* (right)
 - **output:** none.
 - **description:** this is the function that allows the RU to be braked both during the Line Following phase along the MP and within a generic Aol. It will send control signals to the motor drivers, through the *"drive(..)"* function previously described, such that they are driven in the opposite direction to their rotation. To do this, it is necessary to know which is the latter (information provided by the *"orientation"* input) and their module, in order to obtain an instantaneous block of the RU (information provided by the *"motorSpeed"* input).
 - *PIDControl(int pos, double pFac, double iFac, double dFac, int controlType):*
 - **input:** position of the black line of the MP relative to the sensor bar (see infrared sensors library [3]) (*"pos"*); coefficients used for PID control relating to the proportional, integrative and derivative components of the error signal (respectively, *"pFac"*, *"iFac"*, *"dFac"*); parameter that allows the user to choose the type of control to implement (*"controlType"*).
 - **output:** none.
 - **description:** this is the function that implements the PID control of position to perform the Line Following on the MP. Using as feedback the value given in output by the function *"qtr.readLineBlack(..)"*, of the *"QTRsensors"* library [3], which represents the position of the black line of the MP, calculated on the basis of the reflections of the infrared rays emitted by the sensors of the bar, an error is calculated with respect to a reference value. Furthermore, the difference between the error in a given execution cycle and the previous one and the sum of the errors from cycle to cycle are considered, obtaining values proportional respectively to the derivative and the integral in time of the position error. From these, the control law (voltage control of the motors) is obtained, relating to the cases of P control (*"controlType"* = 1), PD control (*"controlType"* = 2) and PID control (*"controlType"* = 3), with which to drive the motors via the *"drive(..)"* function.
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- *driveStraightObs(float dist, char turning)*:
 - input: straight line distance to be travelled (the wheel axis was taken as a reference) expressed in centimetres ("*dist*") and direction of travel ("*turning*").
 - output: none.
 - description: this function allows to travel a distance, given by the input parameter "*dist*", maintaining a straight trajectory and avoiding the slipping problem, by gradually increasing and decreasing the speed respectively near the starting and arrival points. The position calculation is obtained through the encoder counts (see "*convertDist2Steps(...)*" function), also used for the straight motion through a PI control in order to make both wheels travel the same distance. Digital infrared sensors are also used along the perimeter of each RU to detect obstacles and implement routines dedicated to obstacle avoidance. In all phases a check of the serial buffer is performed in order to verify the possible presence of "*stop*" commands from the DUB. The function is also used to perform rotations (see "*turn(...)*" function) since in that case too it is necessary for both wheels to travel the same distance, but in relatively opposite directions.

 - *returnLineObs()*:
 - input: none.
 - output: none.
 - description: this function allows the RU to return to the MP after the data acquisition phase. It works in the same way as the "*driveStraightObs(...)*" function but this time, instead of following a straight motion (considering the obstacle avoidance task) until reaching a certain distance, calculated on the basis of the encoder counts, the robot will advance until it recognizes the black line of the MP via the infrared sensor bar.

 - *turn(int angle)*:
 - input: angle through which to rotate the robot (for simplicity, angles of 90° and 180° in modulus, positive and negative, are accepted) (degrees).
 - output: none.
 - description: this function allows the rotation of the RU by the quantity indicated in input thanks to the angle-length conversion of the circumference arc to be travelled by the wheels (given the diameter of the circumference itself, obtained by the reciprocal distance between the wheel-floor contact points) and the "*driveStraightObs(...)*" function.

 - *reachPoint(float x, float y)*:
 - input: x and y coordinates of the point to be reached, once entered in a given Aol, expressed in the local reference system (cm).
 - output: none.
 - description: this function allows a RU to reach a point with coordinates indicated in input by combining the "*turn(...)*" and "*driveStraightObs(...)*" functions seen previously.
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- *NNmeasurement()*:
 - input: none.
 - output: none.
 - description: this function, combining the last functions described, manages the entire phase of exit from the MP ("*turn(...)*"), permanence in a given AoI ("*reachPoint(...)*"), data acquisition ("*extendLeg(...)*") and return to the MP ("*returnLineObs()*"). It also allows to receive via UART, while reaching a given seismic data collection point, to receive new commands updating the objective and ignoring the previous ones. Therefore, once reached the previously desired position, the front leg is not extended and the RU immediately returns to the MP to reach the updated desired position.

 - *rechargeRobot()*:
 - input: none.
 - output: none.
 - description: this function, once the RU has returned to the MP following a data collection and found the same barcode, manages the exit phase and the reaching of the charging station. It waits for the battery to be fully charged and reconfigures the states of the two finite state machines so as to be ready to receive new commands ("*robotState = LINE_FOLLOWING*"; "*movementState = stop*") and therefore to re-enter the MP.

References

- [1] M.Graziaplina et al., "WP 15, task 15.5 - Final report related to deliverable D15.17 - AHEAD2020 - Flexible Grid Mapping Tool". To be published soon.
- [2] <https://www.pololu.com/product/4225>
- [3] <https://github.com/pololu/qtr-sensors-arduino>
- [4] <https://www.pololu.com/product/4755>
- [5] <https://www.pololu.com/product/2507>